

COLDSPARK DRIVEN ENERGY AND COST-EFFICIENT METHANE CRACKING FOR
HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

D8.1. Project Management Manual (Quality Management)

ColdSpark® project partner	SEID AS
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Work Package number and title	WP8: Project management
Deliverable number	D8.1
Description	This manual will ensure efficient administrative and budgetary management and control and manage the overall operational delivery and ensure work plan project objectives and outcomes are met, thus ensuring quality management.
Lead Beneficiary	SEID AS
Lead Authors	Maya Guevska, EP
Submitted by	Remya Ravindran Nair

Review History

Version	Date	Reviewer	Short Description of Changes
1	25.11.2022	Ass. Prof. Sachin Maruti Chavan, University of Stavanger, Norway	Changes and clarifications related to the PM structure
2	25.11.2022	Dr Remya Ravindran Nair, SEID AS, Norway	Changes and clarifications related to the PM structure and QM process

Document Approval

Name	Role	Action	Date
Terje Hauan	Project Coordinator	<i>Approved</i>	30.11.2022

Nature of the deliverable

R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DMP	Data management plan	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ethics	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	<input type="checkbox"/>
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other	Software, technical diagrams, algorithms, models, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination level

PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online on the Project Results platforms)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	<input type="checkbox"/>

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The ColdSpark® project will validate a novel non-thermal plasma technology to produce hydrogen at an industrial scale from methane, with a process energy efficiency of 79%, achieving a conversion rate of 85% aiming at zero CO₂ emissions. This will be achieved by designing an industrial-relevant reactor that leverages the best features of the non-thermal plasma technologies, gliding arc and corona discharge, to ensure high efficiency and scalability. The innovation addresses for the first time the critical step of matching the reactor with a pulsed power supply. It enables a perfect fine-tuning of the cracking process parameters, to find the right electron density and energy distribution in the plasma reactor, to maximise energy efficiency. The up-and-downstream gas management will be optimised to further contribute to the system's compatibility with the existing infrastructure. The project will develop and test a novel plasma reactor at a lab scale and validate it in conjunction with the power supply at a large scale, pursuing the industry's most power-efficient generation of hydrogen alongside high-value carbon. The technology will assess its application for both, natural gas and biomethane producers. A low energy cost (< 15 kWh/kg H₂ produced) without the need for catalysts and water, makes the proposed solution the most cost-competitive, environment-friendly, and less complex to implement. The reactor design and modularity bring lower CAPEX and OPEX and make it easily scalable and flexible. The project gathers the expertise of a mix of academic, research, and industrial partners from five countries, which bring both outstanding research and topic competence, as well as knowledge and access to the solution for end-user industries.

ColdSpark® is built on a strong consortium of 7 partners from Norway, Spain, Bulgaria, Germany, and the UK with SEID AS as a Coordinator.

More information about the project can be found at: www.coldspark.eu

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this manual is to describe the selected approach for implementing the project activities and achieving its goals. It is describing monitoring and controlling processes to be used

by the partners, project policies and internal rules to be applied and followed, and the overall management approach. The manual will be used by all project partners for day-to-day project (administrative, financial, quality) management.

The document presents the Project Quality Plan and all processes, procedures, and tools to be implemented, and how they will be applied and controlled. This will shape guidance for managing the project throughout its lifecycle and a single point of reference. The document will be adaptable and any of the applied measures can be further developed and improved for effective quality implementation of the project. The document comprises the following sections:

1. Project Structure
2. Project Management
3. Communications and project templates
4. Quality Management
5. Quality assurance and control
6. Risk Management
7. Issue Management
8. Conclusion

ABBREVIATIONS	
Abbreviation	Meaning
EC	European Commission
WP/WPs	Work Package/ Work Packages
GA	Grant Agreement
GAs	General Assembly
PM	Project Management
QM	Quality Management
PTC	Project Technical Committee
AB	Advisory Board
IEC	Innovation and Exploitation Committee
PMs	Project Meetings
PMO	Project Management Officer
TM	Technical Manager
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DoA	Description of the action (annex of the GA)

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1. PROJECT STRUCTURE

1.1. INTRODUCTION

The ColdSpark® project is a 42-month Horizon Europe-funded project with 7 partners from 5 different countries. Project coordinator SEID AS together with the University of Liverpool (UOL) collaborate to develop the novel nonthermal plasma (NTP) methane cracking process based on the know-how from the UOL’s innovative gliding arc (GA) plasma and SEID AS’s industry scale corona plasma system. Their strong expertise in plasma applications at different scales is a critical tool to fine-tune process parameters to achieve maximum energy efficiency and shape the chemical pathways to obtain hydrogen and high-value carbon, like e.g., carbon nanotubes. SEID AS’s new development in advanced power supply makes it possible to tailor the fundamental electron-induced process in plasma to achieve an optimum methane conversion process, aiming at large-scale industrial applications. The University of Stavanger (UiS) will provide the solutions for gas impurities management and hydrogen separation to further optimise the whole NTP methane cracking process. The Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE) will provide the site for prototype testing both at the lab scale and at the large scale. NORCE’s expertise will also support the final process design and optimization. All the technical work will be supported by the International Biogas and Bioenergy Competence Centre (IBBK) which will assess the application of the technology to biomethane plants. The Catalonia Energy Research Institute (IREC-CERCA) will

conduct a full environmental, economic, and technological assessment to study the environmental and cost performance of the solution and demonstrate its competitiveness. Finally, Europroject (EP) brings its expertise in project management and exploitation to run a smooth project development and ensure proper communication and dissemination of results.

The overall plan of the project follows the tasks as scheduled in the Work Plan (in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement). The project is divided into 3 reporting periods, structured in 8 Work Packages, and is expected to provide 33 Deliverables capturing major results and achievements. Project activities can be grouped into five blocks:

- 1) Technology development and optimization
- 2) Validation and industrial modelling
- 3) Environmental and techno-economic assessment
- 4) Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities
- 5) Project management

Number	Roles	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	Coordinator	Seid AS	SEID AS	NO
2	Beneficiary	IREC-CERCA	FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	ES
3	Beneficiary	UiS	UNIVERSITETET I STAVANGER	NO
4	Beneficiary	NORCE	NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE AS	NO
5	Beneficiary	EUROPROJECT EP	EVROPROJECT OOD	BG
6	Beneficiary	IBBK	IBBK FACHGRUPPE BIOGAS GMBH	DE
7	Associated Partner	UOL	THE UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL	UK

Table 1 ColdSpark® project partners

1.2. WORK PLAN

The research and innovation (R&I) project will be implemented through 8 work packages. WP1 will design, build and test two lab-scale prototypes for plasma methane cracking and provide the key system parameters for the design of the large-scale prototype. WP2 will provide an effective concept for gas separation and management of impurities. Within WP3 the plasma reactor and the power supply will be optimized, upscaled and matched, and a function test will be carried out. The large-scale prototype will be tested and validated in WP4. WP5 will create an industrial desktop front-end engineering design to validate the industrial feasibility and use model data and WP6 will evaluate the sustainability of innovations through LCA and LCC methods. WP7 will be dealing with Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities and will help the exploitation of the technologies developed within ColdSpark®. WP8 will assure smooth implementation and project management.

Figure 1 ColdSpark® PERT diagram – WPs

1.3. TIMELINE

The timeframe of the planned Work Packages is described in Annex 1 (GANTT Work packages). All partners will have access to a detailed GANTT with tasks' timeframes and distribution of person-months (created during the setting-up stage) and a supportive chart with important project deadlines/events (e.g., deadlines for submission of deliverables, internal deadlines for submission of reports, drafts of documents; scheduled partner and other meetings, planned completion of important tasks, important milestones, etc.), describing a detailed schedule for a 6-month period.

2. PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management processes will assure:

- efficient administrative and budgetary management and control
- operational delivery and management of scientific, human, and financial resources
- achieving project objectives and outcomes and progress according to the plan
- appropriate measures are taken in the management of identified and emerging risks and issues during the project implementation
- proper coordination and supervision of the project activities
- scientific, technical and innovation management.

2.1. PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

The project management structure of ColdSpark® and the procedures to be applied are described in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) and will be further detailed in this document. The project management structure is presented below in Figure 2. It includes lists of different processes, policies, tools, and roles, organized around these basic pillars presenting the necessary inputs, resources and outputs to be provided during the project execution, control, and closure – all are following PM and QM principles and defined specifically for the implementation of this project. A presentation of the structure of the PM bodies (having different levels of responsibilities in applying the set tools, processes, and policies) follows in section 2.2, Figure 3.

Figure 2 PM structure

The day-to-day management will be conducted at four levels:

1. sub-task,
2. task,
3. work package,
4. overall project.

The PM toolkit includes:

- deliverable template

- reporting templates and progress evaluating templates (financial reports, internal progress reports, supporting documents, logs, lists and records)
- meeting templates (meeting agenda, minutes)
- additional detailed GANTT chart with deadlines.

All management templates are available on the shared partner workspace in Teams. Some of them are presented in the following sections of the current document. Content of the rest is defined as sensitive and not to be shared outside of the Consortium (e.g., GANTT with the distribution of person-months, internal templates for financial reporting and other internal tools for monitoring).

Project processes and policies will assure smooth implementation and excellent results in the originally given timeframe. All partners will conform to the set high standards.

2.2. PROJECT MANAGEMENT BODIES

The Project Management Bodies structure was presented during the ColdSpark® Kickoff meeting and minor changes took place, as follows:

- General Assembly (GAs) will be the ultimate decision-making body (instead of the originally planned Project Board). GAs' responsibilities are described in Chapter 6 - Governance structure of the CA.
- Advisory Board (AB) has been established, including the User Advisory Board

The project's governing bodies include:

- **General Assembly (GAs)** - the ultimate decision body
- **Project Technical Committee (PTC),**
- **Advisory Board (AB),** including User Advisory Board
- **Innovation and Exploitation Committee (IEC)**

Figure 3 is presenting the management bodies in the project and existing interconnections, representing communication flow and reporting processes (other not displayed links are possible through the project implementation). All bodies can freely exchange information and structured processes regarding official and internal reporting and related responsibilities are described further in this document. SEID's management team is forming the core management structure: PC as intermediary between the EC and the Consortium, the PMO is the main contact person and leads the internal Consortium communication and processes, and the TM who is responsible for the technical implementation of the project.

Figure 3 ColdSpark® Management Bodies

2.2.1. GENERAL ASSEMBLY (GAS)

It is composed of one representative per partner, with the authority to represent its institution to the decisions of the board. All meetings will be chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC). They will deliberate on all matters related to a) project strategic orientation and planning; b) risk assessment and conflict resolution; c) approval of the reports to be submitted to the EC; d) contract amendments. Detailed information is given in Chapter 6 - Governance structure of the CA.

2.2.2. PROJECT TECHNICAL COMMITTEE (PTC)

The committee was set during the Kickoff meeting including the Technical Work Package Leaders (WP1-6) and chaired by the Technical Manager (TM). The Technical Manager decided to include all partners in the Technical Committee and to extend its scope by adding the WP7 Leader - EP, Task Leader from WP1 – UoL and very active partner in different WPs – IBBK. Thus, the committee consist of representatives of all 7 involved organizations who meet on a monthly basis. The PTC will report specific situations which may affect the planned course of the project to the PC and to the Project management officer (PMO) that will ensure adequate institutional liaison with the GAs in case of emerging problems. The key responsibilities of the PTC will include a) detailed planning and management of the tasks within ColdSpark® WPs; b) monitoring the technical progress against set deadlines for milestones and deliverables; c) reporting to the PC and GAs on the status and the risks associated in the implementation of tasks within WPs; d) ensuring good communication and

leadership within all project teams. The Technical Manager is responsible for complying with the internal project procedures.

2.2.3. ADVISORY BOARD (AB)

The AB will include external stakeholders and experts who will be engaged from the beginning of the project in different project activities. It will consist of 3-4 members (including the User Advisory Board):

- Scientific Advisor
- Representative of the end-user company
- Representative/s of professional associations, including from the Oil & Gas and Biogas & Biomethane industries, as potential H₂ producers.

The AB will analyze the users' needs and consult ColdSpark® Consortium. It will be also involved in Project meetings, face-to-face or virtual working meetings, project workshops and other occasions.

The AB is expected to provide its feedback to the PC and the GAs, including identified technical, economic, and regulatory barriers and to help build a wide network of project stakeholders.

2.2.4. INNOVATION & EXPLOITATION COMMITTEE (IEC)

IEC will take care of a) the preparation of ColdSpark® exploitation plan to ensure that the outcomes of the project will be protected, valorized, and adequately exploited, b) the support for knowledge transfer between the project partners, c) adequate protection of the project results. It will be chaired by the Exploitation Manager and will meet during the Project Meetings and will conduct a virtual meeting once in three months. The first and next versions of it will be included in the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC), and DEC updates while a final separate version will be provided at the end of the project. The members will be responsible for compiling the plan and discovering exploitation opportunities:

- Exploitation Manager
- Communications Manager
- IBBK representative
- Selected external AB member

2.3. ROLES

The project management roles established within ColdSpark® include:

- Project Coordinator (PC) is represented by Terje Hauan from SEID AS, who has extensive experience in project management and industrial engineering. The PC is going to be the

intermediary between the consortium members and the Commission services and will be responsible for all activities needed to ensure effective and efficient financial and administrative project coordination as well as effective communication among all partners and with the EC. The PC will ensure the overall project supervision and will accomplish the financial and administrative coordination closely collaborating with the rest of the management team.

- Technical Manager (TM), Yangfang Li, SEID AS – will chair the Project Technical Committee (PTC), and will be responsible for organization of monthly PTC meetings and smooth technical implementation of the project.
- Project Management Officer (PMO), Remya Ravindran Nair, SEID AS - will assist the PC in all project management and coordination activities, including the requested reports. The PMO will be assigned at SEID AS and will be supported by Europroject (for administrative and financial matters). PMO will be in charge of 1) financial management and reporting; 2) legal, contractual, and administrative management; 3) internal consortium communication and communication with EC.
- Project Manager (supportive role) assigned at EP (Maya Guevska) will assist the Project Management Officer in day-to-day administrative and financial tasks during the starting phase of the project and during reporting periods, including the elaboration of PM templates, communication among the partners, correct and timely preparation of the technical and financial reporting.
- Exploitation Manager (Terje Hauan) - will chair the Innovation and Exploitation Committee (IEC).
- Communication Manager (Galina Ivanova, EP) – will coordinate communication and dissemination activities during the whole project life, based Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication. The plan may be fine-tuned and updated during the project implementation according to potential inputs received from the PTC, and by dedicated contact persons to be identified within each partner.
- Work Package Leaders are responsible for internal progress reporting and monitoring the implementation of the respective WP. They are responsible for reviewing all deliverables elaborated within the WP under their leadership.
- Task Leaders will be responsible for internal control of the implementation of the tasks and permanent communication with the WP Leaders.

In case of a possible change in the persons taking these positions, the PC should be immediately informed. In case of changing PC, EC should be immediately informed.

2.4. PARTNER CONTACT DETAILS AND DISTRIBUTION LISTS

The ColdSpark® contact list is shared in the shared partner workspace and available for all partners. It is regularly revised and updated. In case of changes regarding the project management roles and contact persons for each organization the Coordinator SEID AS should be informed. Separate group mailing lists are created (e.g., for PTC, GAs, WPs, etc.), as well as partner distribution lists based on the website domain to enable smoother and easier communication among specific groups.

2.5. PROJECT MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGY

The Open PM² is a project management methodology developed and supported by the European Commission. Its purpose is to enable project teams to manage their projects effectively and deliver solutions and benefits to their organisations and stakeholders. PM² is based on operational experience from projects run within European Institutions but also incorporates elements from a wide range of globally accepted project management best practices, standards, and methodologies such as PMBoK Guide, PRINCE2®, IPMA-ICB. The methodology is suitable for any type of project and ideal for projects related to the public sector, or EU programmes and grants.

Open PM² provides open access to PM² to all European Union institutions, EU Member States, contractors, and the general public. The PM² guide provides a project governance model (i.e., roles & responsibilities); a project lifecycle (i.e., project phases); a set of processes (i.e., project management activities); a set of project artefacts (i.e., templates and guidelines); a set of mindsets (i.e., effective beliefs and behaviours).

Based on the PM² Methodology ColdSpask will follow basic principles, utilize, and adapt:

- a project governance structure
- process guidelines
- artefact templates
- guidelines for using the artefacts
- a set of effective mindsets

PM² improves the effectiveness of project management by:

- improving communication and the dissemination of information
- clarifying expectations as early as possible in the project lifecycle
- defining the project lifecycle (from Initiating to Closing)
- providing guidelines for project planning
- introducing monitor and control activities
- proposing management activities and outputs (plans, meetings, decisions)
- providing a link to agile practices (Agile PM²)

The ColdSpark® project will use open guidelines and templates (PM² Artefacts) provided within PM² for the different phases of project implementation to assure high standards and smooth quality management. Templates have been / will be adjusted for the project. (More information about PM² - The European Commission's Official Project Management Methodology - Open to All can be found at the official website of the European Union.)

3. COLDSPARK® COMMUNICATIONS AND PROJECT TEMPLATES

Internal communications procedures and tools, as well as established templates, will be used to improve communication, smooth project execution, proper monitoring, and as a uniform set of documentation and processes.

3.1. INTERNAL COMMUNICATIONS

The coordinator organized the kick-off meeting in mid-June 2022 and defined the schedule and frequency of other working and project meetings. The following meetings were determined as a crucial part of the implementation and quality management of the ColdSpark® project:

- **Weekly / Bi-weekly** meetings between **SEID and EP** to review and discuss project management, communication, and dissemination issues.
- **Weekly / Bi-weekly Working and WP meetings** organized by WP and Task Leaders for close collaboration and permanent communication (organized when necessary).
- Project Technical Committee (PTC) - **Monthly meetings of the PTC** to be organized by SEID and led by the Technical Manager to review progress.
- Project Meetings (PMs) will be organized twice a year by the hosting partners with the assistance of the Coordinator.
- GAs will meet on the occasion of the Project meeting and additional virtual meetings will take place in case important questions and issues are raised by the partners and its members.
- Internal Quality Review meetings – every six months, organized by SEID and EP as a part of the Project Meetings or virtually.
- Advisory Board meetings will be held during Project meetings and will be organized separately on the occasion of ColdSpark® events/workshops or virtually when necessary.
- Innovation and Exploitation Committee (IEC) - It will be chaired by the Exploitation Manager and will meet during the Project Meetings and virtually once in three months.
- Other ad-hoc meetings

3.1.1. SCHEDULE

The following schedule (Table 2) is defined during the first months of the project. Changes may occur during the project implementation. Decisions about the place of Project Meetings will be taken every meeting for the next one by GAs.

Meeting	Calendar
PTC	At the end of each month
Project meetings (PMs - partners, including GAs)	June 2022 - KOM December 2022 – 2 nd Project Meeting in Barcelona, Spain. June 2023 – 3 rd ; December 2023 – 4 th . June 2024 – 5 th ; December 2024 – 6 th . End of October/ Beginning of November 2025 Final Project Meeting and Final demonstration event*
AB meetings	During PMs
IEC meetings	During PMs, virtual every 3 months

*More information on Dissemination events will be given in the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC)

Table 2 Meeting schedules

3.1.2. TOOLS

The following represents the means of communication within the ColdSpark® Consortium.

EMAIL

Email is the primary communication tool. Several communication levels have been identified:

1. Intra-WP: mostly between two or several partners on specific issues, technical communication, and ad-hoc.
2. Inter-WP and PTC: addressing the issues between different WPs, interfacing, and dependencies. The communication is organized by the relevant WP leads, Technical Manager, and PMO.
3. General Assembly and partner-level delegates are defined in chapter 2, section 2.2 of this document. The communications are organized by the project coordinator and the PMO.
4. External communication with stakeholders (will be described in the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication).

Email communication is organized into different groups: Main Contact List available in the shared workspace with separate contacts (described in chapter 2, section 2.4). External contact lists will be maintained by the Coordinator and WP7 Leader, in addition, other partners will maintain their contact lists with interested parties (e.g., IBBK) which will be available for the rest of the partners upon request.

During the ColdSpark® Kick-off Meeting, the TM presented some communication channels and rules: 1) Email correspondence - Email Subject: ColdSpark® – WP x – Task x.x – Partner – member (name – optional); 2) email with relevant people in Cc; 3) email correspondence will be saved in project records.

ONLINE MEETINGS / WEB CONFERENCING

Modern communication tools enable collaborative work and may lead to the improvement of cooperation between different partners. The 4 above-described levels were identified regarding the online meetings and web conferencing tools.

For the ColdSpark® project, partners will mainly use Microsoft Teams for team meetings – partner to partner, PTC, Review and other ad-hoc meetings. Microsoft teams allow for online face-to-face meetings, screen sharing, co-authoring files, and whiteboarding in Microsoft Teams.

Skype, ZOOM and other tools can be used occasionally if needed.

PHYSICAL MEETINGS

Partners will gather for Project meetings every six months (twice a year). The host partner will be responsible for organization and logistics support. AB members can join in person or virtually. Due to external circumstances a physical meeting can be cancelled (upon agreement by all partners) and organized virtually.

3.2. PROJECT TEMPLATES AND REPOSITORY

3.2.1. PM TEMPLATES

ColdSpark® templates have been designed and elaborated by EP with the supervision and final approval of SEID AS based on:

- templates of the Open PM² project management methodology.
- Standards and rules are set out within the project's graphic charter.
- Rules set out in the Grant Agreement.
- Horizon Europe Reference Documents by EC (publicly available).
- Organizational templates used by the partners in different HE and H2020 projects.

ColdSpark® general C&D templates (ColdSpark_headletter_page, ColdSpark_Title_page, ColdSpark_Word_document_template, ColdSpark_pptx_template) and other specific C&D templates are available in the shared workspace in Teams and presented in D7.1. Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication. Meeting Agenda, Meeting minutes, and 1-page Meeting minutes are presented below.

MEETING AGENDA

Meeting Agenda
ColdSpark Project Meeting (number)
Place – city/town, country
dates

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Meeting objectives and general information

..
.....
.....

Additional information

Wifi

User:
Password:

CONTACTS HOSTING PARTNER

Name: Etwil

AGENDA
1st Day
Venue

Table version 2

Table version 2

Instructions → Information to be included: Partner names, speaker names (if applicable), item of discussion (e.g., Wf, tasks, project relevant topic, etc.), time and duration, information about breaks and different activities should be included, venues, addresses, logistic information, other relevant information.

Participant Name	Invited (I) / Confirmed (C)	Project Partner / Organization	Mode of participation (on-site, on-line)

Figure 4 Meeting Agenda

MEETINGS MINUTES

Meeting Minutes
ColdSpark Project Meeting (number)
Place – city/town, country |
dates

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Participant Name	Date of participation	Project Partner / Organization	Mode of participation (on-site, on-line)

Meeting objectives and summary

..
.....
.....
.....

Instructions →

- > Summary of each session (summary of presentations, Questions and Answers sessions, major topics and issues discussed)
- > Decision taken (agreed)
- > Conclusions
- > Next steps (if applicable)

Figure 5 Meeting Minutes

1-PAGE MEETING MINUTES

COLDSPARK MEETING TITLE

TIME:

PURPOSE:

PARTICIPATING PARTNERS:

TOPICS DISCUSSED

> ..

> ..

ISSUES IDENTIFIED

> ..

> ..

DECISIONS TAKEN

> ..

> ..

OTHERS

> ..

EFFICIENCY:	CREATED BY:
EXCELLENT <input type="checkbox"/> VERY GOOD <input type="checkbox"/> AVERAGE <input type="checkbox"/> BELOW AVERAGE <input type="checkbox"/>	

Figure 6 1-page Meeting Minutes

3.2.2. REPOSITORY

The project is utilizing Microsoft 365 Business premium with storage in Europe and has an online backup solution with extra security and backup from EMP Secure. Two-factor security on user accounts is implemented. Raw data is archived on a local server in our lab, calibrated data is shared through Microsoft Teams and SharePoint. All project documents are organized in folders available for the Consortium partners (password protected). A decision to only use Teams as a shared

workspace has been taken in the starting phase of the project (instead of the originally planned OwnCloud attached to the project website). This will allow a smoother process because: only one place will be used instead of multiple which may cause confusion; Teams allow more functionalities related to collaborative work and meetings, chats, calendars, etc.

4. QUALITY MANAGEMENT

4.1. OBJECTIVES AND PROCESS

The Project Quality management process aims to ensure the achievement of high-quality project results and smooth project implementation regarding the completion of the project’s tasks on time, on budget, in scope and in line with the contractual obligations with the EC. Quality assurance and control procedures will provide a solid ground for ensuring compliance with all relevant rules and provisions. The procedures and rules described below will ensure that the current project will meet the expected results as planned and that deliverables will be accepted by the relevant stakeholders.

Figure 7 QM phases

Quality-related activities are identification and planning, execution, and monitoring and control of the project (Figure 7).

The next sections outline the Quality Plan of ColdSpark® and include:

- quality characteristics – to identify the objectives, approach, requirements, activities and responsibilities of the project's quality management process and how it will be implemented throughout the project, documented in this plan based on the project objectives, approach, deliverables, expected benefits and resources available; Quality standards, guidelines, tools, and techniques (e.g., Deliverables Acceptance Checklist, deliverables acceptance criteria and procedure, periodic reports and internal progress reporting criteria and procedures, etc.),

- quality assurance activities to be performed as planned, compliance with EU’s and other relevant rules and regulations (compliance verification), related responsibilities, e.g., review meetings, activities reporting among others,
- quality control activities to be performed as planned and opportunity for quality improvements, e.g., project management artefacts review and quality plan reviews,
- Risk, Issue Management and related control activities.

Project quality management will ensure successful completion and maintain a desired level of excellence. Any quality activities related to project artefacts and deliverables, quality assurance and control are documented in this plan.

4.2. RESPONSIBILITIES

All partners involved are intended to follow the procedures identified in the current document.

A ColdSpark® responsibility matrix (RM), based on the ARSCI Model for Assigning Responsibilities¹ defining five different degrees of responsibility, will be used and include the following degrees:

A – Accountable - ultimately answerable for the correct and thorough completion of the deliverable or task, the one who ensures the prerequisites of the task are met and who delegates the work to those responsible. There should always be a single Role Accountable for any given management activity or artefact, to approve work that the responsible provides.

R – Responsible is responsible for doing the work (e.g. creation of an artefact). When responsibility is delegated, the delegator becomes accountable for the performance of the delegated work. There should always be a single role Responsible for any given management activity or artefact.

S – Support - work with the person Responsible to complete the given activity or artefact. Support role helps complete the task.

C – Consulted - need to provide information or insights to the person responsible so that they can complete a given management activity or artefact, typically subject-matter experts in two-way communication.

I - Informed - need to be kept informed of the progress or/and the result of the activity or artefact in one-way communication.

The following table defines the responsibilities of those involved in quality management:

Responsibility matrix	GA	PC	PTC	AB	IEC	TM	PMO
Quality Management Plan	I	C	I	I	-	C	R

¹ Kourounakis, N., Project Governance and the ARSCI Model, 2019

Perform Quality Assurance	I	A	A	C	-	R	R
Perform Quality Control	I	A	R	-	-	C	R
Perform Deliverables Acceptance	I	A	S	-	C	R	A
Perform Final Project Acceptance	I	A	S	-	C	A	R

Table 3 ColdSpark® responsibility matrix

The **Project Coordinator** (PC), as WP8 Leader, is accountable for the supervision of the quality assurance activities.

Technical Manager (TM), as chair of the Project Technical Committee, will be responsible for performing quality assurance and control activities.

The **Project Management Officer** (PMO) is responsible for the overall QM process, including scheduling the reviewing and acceptance activities and ensuring that they are performed according to the plan, ensuring the correct and full completion of the quality assurance activities as well as assistance in performing quality control throughout the project. The project manager from Europroject is responsible for providing and adjusting templates for all PM and QM procedures, including a financial report, and supporting the PMO in administrative tasks and during periodic reporting.

The respective **WP, task, or deliverable lead** are accountable for deliverables and outputs production and acceptance and for ensuring the availability of resources (including people) and providing guidelines. **The deliverable lead** is responsible for the completion of the respective deliverable, **WP Leaders** are responsible to review all deliverables within their work package. **Task leaders** are responsible for monitoring and achieving results within their respective tasks and completion on time.

4.3. TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

The following tools and techniques will be used for project planning, management, and control:

- Monthly WP Status Report – completed by WP leaders and provided to PMO.
- 6-month Progress Reports – completed by WP leaders and provided to PMO.
- Deliverable Peer Reviews – assigned to different reviewers/review teams.
- Deliverable Review and Acceptance Checklist - completed by PMO for each deliverable.
- Project and Quality Review Meetings – incl., milestone review, as part of Project meetings or organized by PMO and other partners when needed
- Project Internal monitoring supportive tools

The above-mentioned templates are part of the PM toolkit (described in Section 2.1.) available for all partners, in the shared workspace, Folder – General, WP8, PM toolkit (templates).

4.4. METRICS

This section includes the quality criteria to be collected and reported during the project implementation;

Criterion Name	Frequency	Tolerance
Artefacts and deliverable review	Per project phase - once (or more if needed*)	No tolerance
Monthly WP status reports	Monthly	1 week
PTC meeting	Monthly (described in Section 3.1.)	1 week
6-month WP Progress Reports	Bi-annually	2 weeks
WP Project Review (following completion of WP Progress Report)	Bi-annually	1 month
Project meetings AB meetings	Bi-annually (described in Section 3.1.)	1 month
Weekly and bi-weekly working, review, and WP meetings	Weekly and Bi-weekly (described in Section 3.1.)	1 week
Milestone reviews executed	Per project phase - once (or more if needed*)	No tolerance
Stakeholders' satisfaction (based on meetings and structured discussions) **	Yearly (3 times for the project lifetime)	2 months
Reporting period reviews final project review	Per reporting period - once (or more if needed*)	No tolerance

*Rejections by the EC of deliverables achieved milestones, and periodic reports are possible. In such situations partner will need to re-work, perform the requested changes and review again until the work is accepted.

**More information on stakeholders 'events will be given in the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC).

5. QUALITY ASSURANCE AND CONTROL

5.1. QUALITY ASSURANCE ACTIVITIES

The project quality assurance process is structured in such a way as to comprise all levels and types of project activities and to ensure high-quality project communication, delivery, issue and risk management. The goal is to verify the performance and compliance of project - activities with the defined quality requirements. The quality assurance activities and requirements are defined based on the overall PM approach and have been described in detail under Section 4. The results of the

quality assurance activities will be documented in the relevant quality and status reports. The Project Coordinator (PC) is overall accountable for the quality assurance activities within the project. The PMO is responsible for scheduling and initiating all project quality reviews and procedures. The quality assurance activities include, but are not limited to the following:

- Evaluating the design of the project controls, by confirming that they are implemented, and by assessing their operational effectiveness.
- Compliance verification with EU's policies, rules, and regulations, as well as with other relevant rules, regulations and legislation.
- Artefact / Deliverable reviews and approvals, review before it is considered finalised and submitted to EC for formal approval.
- Monthly Work Package Status Reports and 6-month Progress Reports
- Project Review Meetings, Project PCT Meetings, other planned consortium meetings and communications.
- Milestone Reviews
- Project Acceptance Review

5.2. DELIVERABLES REVIEW

Deliverables Acceptance - to verify each deliverable compliance with the predefined objectives and set of criteria, and to obtain formal multilevel approval before their submission to the EC. The responsibilities are set in Section 4.2. of the document.

The total number of Deliverables in ColdSpark® to be submitted to the European Commission over the project implementation is 33 - 9 of which will be freely accessible to the public. The following review process is established to guarantee high-quality performance and completion.

5.2.1. REQUIREMENTS

There are two types of deliverables foreseen in the project:

R - Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DMP - Data management plan

All Report deliverables must be prepared in Microsoft Word format. For collaboration, partners may use other tools. To ensure consistency, a template is constantly available on the shared workspace in Folder – General, WP8, PM toolkit (templates) and Folder – General, FINAL deliverables. All deliverables must use the template provided, be written in English and be proofread. When submitting the final deliverable, it must be converted to PDF format, before

uploading it. All deliverables will be submitted by the Coordinator. For deliverables that do not take the form of a written report, a written record can be prepared including supporting materials.

The content of each deliverable depends on the type of deliverable itself. It should cover all the information relevant to the activity that it results, in and all the information needed by other Partners for performing their activities. The responsibility is of its author(s). The deliverable should meet a set of requirements, based on the following aspects:

Regarding Content:

1. Relevance. Presented information should be true to the original objectives set out in Annex A of the GA and is relevant for the achievement of the Project goals and focused on the key issues.
2. Accuracy. Information presented must be reliable - all claims need to be proven and/or supported by relevant references.
3. Completeness. The deliverable should include all the necessary information to achieve its purpose.
4. Concision. The deliverable should include only necessary and relevant information and eliminate redundancies.

The deliverables are to have a uniform appearance, structure and referencing scheme. The partner should align to the following guiding principles in terms of appearance, structure, and overall presentation:

1. Clarity
 - Sentences are short, engaging and grammatically correct.
 - The layout and formatting of the document help readers follow along and make sense of the content.
 - Abbreviations are used only when necessary and are outlined at the beginning of the document.
2. Consistency
 - Ensure there is consistency between different sections, internal document references, related requirements, documents, and other deliverables.
 - Ensure that all tables, figures, and charts have been properly referenced.
3. Use of language
 - Use specific, definite, and concrete language
 - Check spelling, grammar, and punctuation
 - Have the deliverable proofread before sending it to reviewers.

All of the requirements described above are transferred into a Deliverables Reviewing Checklist to be used on different review levels (at least on the second round) by PMO and/or TM.

5.2.2. PROCEDURE

RESPONSIBILITIES

In addition to the roles described in Section 4.2.:

The deliverable lead is responsible for the completion of the respective deliverable,

WP Leaders are responsible to review all deliverables within their work package,

Task leaders are responsible for monitoring and achieving results within their respective tasks and completing them on time,

- At least one additional reviewer/review team will be invited to contribute with recommendations and inputs (preferably participants outside (not actively participating in the production/writing) of the relevant deliverable or task).
- The PMO and TM will review deliverables subject to technical WPs (from WP1 to WP6)
- PMO or the PC will be submitting the deliverable on the Portal Continuous Reporting, Deliverables Section, on behalf of the Coordinator.
- Final acceptance - PC approves all project deliverables before final submission. The Project Coordinator may return them for additional refinement if necessary.

At least two rounds of review are foreseen for the planned deliverables:

1st review round – the document will be sent for an internal review by Review Team 1 consisting of the WP Leader, PMO and Technical Manager (WP1 to WP6), to approve the structure of the deliverable. The Deliverable’s lead and authors are responsible for completion.

2nd review round - the first complete draft of the deliverable must be sent to Review Team 2: TM (WP 1 to WP6), PMO, WP Leader, additional reviewer, and PC. If not accepted, it is returned for alterations to the deliverable’s lead.

The additional reviewers can be suggested by the deliverable’s lead, WP Lead, or the Coordinator and will be assigned for each deliverable at least 3 months before final submission in the Deliverables List ColdSpark® table in a shared workspace: Folder – General, FINAL deliverables.

TIMING

When	What
At least two months (60 days) before the deadline	High-level skeleton expected length must be submitted to the Review Team 1

Up to 45 days before the deadline	Review team 1 responses, approving or guidance for improvement/changes
At least 1 month (30 days) before the deadline	The first complete draft must be submitted to the review team/s – Review Team 2.
At least 15 days before the deadline	Review team 2 responds with potential additional requests for revisions, allowing ten more days for revisions
At least 5 before the deadline	The final deliverable must be submitted to the Coordinator
Before the deadlines / on the last working day of the month indicated in the GA	The project coordinator gives final approval and submits

Table 4 Deliverable Review timeline

Note: partners responsible for the deliverables are specified in the DoA. Any risk of delay should be communicated in advance to the Coordinator (either by the deliverable’s lead or the WP Lead).

5.2.3. CHECKLIST

The deliverable reviews are performed in 2 phases (for the 1st and the 2nd round of review) by the PMO and/or TM based on the Deliverables Reviewing Checklist (empty template is available in the shared workspace and completed checklists will be available in Folder – General, Final deliverables. The assessment - findings, recommendations and remediation/improvement actions should be directly provided to the Deliverable’s lead who is responsible to do corrections / improvements.

5.2.4. DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

ColdSpark® Deliverable Template is presented below. The final title of the file should include the name of the project _ number of the deliverables _and the short title.

COLDSPARK DRIVEN ENERGY AND COST-EFFICIENT METHANE CRACKING FOR HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

D.... /number/ ./name

Coldspark® project partner: Choose an item.
 Due date: Click or tap to enter a date.
 Issue date: Click or tap to enter a date.

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Document Information

Deliverable title /Insert title of Deliverable according to DoA/
Work Package number and title /Insert title of related Work Package/
Deliverable number /Insert numbering of Deliverable according to DoA, e.g. D5.1.1, 2, etc./
Description /Insert description of Deliverable according to DoA + more details if needed/
Lead Beneficiary Choose an item.
Lead Authors Person's name
Contributors Person's name
Submitted by Person's name

Review History

Version	Date	Reviewer	Short Description of Changes
1	dd.mm.yyyy		
2		UP Leader	
3		Technical Manager	

Document Approval

Name	Role	Action	Date
Terje Haugen	Project Coordinator	Approved	

Nature of the deliverable

R Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
ENG Investigative papers, filings, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DATA Data sets, microdata, etc.
DMAP Data management plan
Ethics Deliverables related to ethics issues
SECURITY Deliverables related to security issues
Other Software, technical diagrams, algorithms, models, etc.

Dissemination level

PU Public – Fully open (automatically) posted online on the Project Results platform)
SEN Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This report forms part of the deliverables from the project Coldspark® which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 101069991.

The Coldspark® project will validate a novel non-thermal plasma technology to produce hydrogen at an industrial scale from methane, with a process energy efficiency of 78%, achieving a conversion rate of 85% aiming at zero CO₂ emissions. This will be achieved by designing an industrial-relevant reactor that leverages the best features of the non-thermal plasma technologies: gliding arc and corona discharge, to ensure high efficiency and scalability. The innovation addresses for the first time the critical step of matching the reactor with a pulsed power supply. It enables a perfect fine-tuning of the cracking process parameters, to find the right electron density and energy distribution in the plasma reactor to maximise energy efficiency. The up-and-downstream gas management will be optimised to further contribute to the system's compatibility with the existing infrastructure. The project will develop and test a novel plasma reactor at a lab scale and validate it in conjunction with the power supply at a large scale, pursuing the industry's most power-efficient generation of hydrogen alongside high-value carbon. The technology will assess its application for both, natural gas and biomethane producers. A low energy cost (< 15 kWh/kg H₂ produced), without the need for catalysts and water, makes the proposed solution the most cost-competitive, environment-friendly, and least complex to implement. The reactor design and modularity bring lower CAPEX and OPEX and make it easily scalable and flexible. The project gathers the expertise of a mix of academic, research, and industrial partners from five countries, which bring both outstanding research and topic competence, as well as knowledge and access to the solution for end-user industries.

Coldspark® is built on a strong consortium of 7 partners from Norway, Spain, Bulgaria, Germany, and the UK with IEMA AS as a Coordinator.

More information about the project can be found at: www.coldspark.eu

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Short description of the document and its purpose

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GA...

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Figure 8 Deliverable template

5.3. QUALITY REVIEWS

5.3.1. WORK PERFORMANCE QUALITY REVIEWS

MONTHLY WORK PACKAGE STATUS REPORT

The project quality will be monitored and managed through periodic reporting to EC and internal reporting on the work package status, use of resources, risks and issues encountered and planning. Once per month each Work Package leader will fill in a 1-page Work Package Status Report. The PMO reminds each Work Package Leader and collects the reports to be revised by PMO. They will be discussed during the PTC meetings. The project manager from Europroject is assigned to adjust and provide the template. The template below is already defined but changes and improvements are possible throughout the project's lifetime.

Monthly Work Package Status Report - ColdSpark project
Work package No: and title

Reporting period: <mm.dd.yyyy> to <mm.dd.yyyy>

Work Package Leader (WPL): ... PHASE: Executing	Overall Status: Green / Orange / Red Green = GOOD Orange = AT RISK Red = OFF THE TRACK
Task_lead: Task_lead: Task_lead: Task_lead:	DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES D.. D.. MS
ACTIVITIES PERFORMED AND PLANNED Performed: > <Short description of ongoing project action/task 1>, status <ongoing / complete / pending> > <Short description of ongoing project action/task 2>, status <ongoing / complete / pending> > Planned: > <Short description of next planned key project action/task / next steps > >	WORK PACKAGE INDICATORS (PROJECT INDICATORS RELEVANT TO THE WORK PACKAGE, KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS) > Baselined delivery date: <xx/xx/xx> > Forecasted delivery date: <xx/xx/xx> > Variance: <+ xx months> TOP WORK PACKAGE RISKS AND ISSUES Status: Green <Shortly describe any related risks or identified issues> > Risk <number 1>, level <Low, Medium, High>, action 1 > Risk <number 2>, level <xxx>, action <xxx> > Issue <number 1>, severity <Major, Moderate, Minor>, action 1 >
WORK PACKAGE STATUS SUMMARY <Short narrative description of current status>	DECISIONS TAKEN <xx/xx/xx>, <id xx>: <describe decision 1> <xx/xx/xx>, <id xx>: <describe decision 2>
OTHER COMMENTS →	WORK PACKAGE CHANGES <Short narrative description of changes (if any)>

Figure 9 Monthly WP Status Report

6-MONTH WP PROGRESS REPORT

Work Package Leaders will be asked to report every 6 months all activities they have performed, risks or issues encountered within the respective work package using the Work Package Progress Report template (Figure 8). The PMO reminds each Work Package Leader and collects the reports to be revised by PMO (WP1 to WP6). They will be discussed during the Project meetings or in dedicated virtual meetings. WP Leaders are responsible to gather all the information on the technical progress in their WP from the task leaders and participants. Project manager from Europroject is assigned to adjust and provide the templates. The template below is already defined but changes and improvements are possible throughout the project's lifetime.

Figure 10 6-month WP Progress Report

COLD SPARK

6-month WP Project Progress Report

Reporting period 01/06/2022 – 30/11/2022

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Document Control Information

Settings	Visual
Document Title	COLD SPARK 6-month WP Project Progress Report
Responsible Partner	
Event	[Insert Date]

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1. Work Packages Overview

1.1. Summary of the work performed for the reporting period (6 months)

Work Package Information	
Work Package Leader:	
Work Package Identifier:	
Other partners involved:	
Other stakeholders, if applicable:	

The goal of WP... is to ...

1.2. On-going and Planned Activities

WP... is an schedule with its deliverables, tasks, results or not? Describe shortly

1.3. Deliverables

This section addresses completed and ongoing deliverable:

Number (according to DoA)	Deliverable Name	Target Delivery Date	Actual Delivery date	Status	Comments
				Choose an item.	<i>Describe shortly the status of the Deliverable, any delays, issues?</i>

1.4. Milestones (MS)

This section addresses completed and ongoing milestones:

Number (according to DoA)	Milestone Name	Target Delivery Date	Actual Delivery date	Status	Comments
				Choose an item.	<i>Describe shortly the status of the MS, any delays, issues?</i>

2. Work Package Details

2.1. Major Risks and Actions Taken

<This section should highlight the work package risks (potential obstacles/issues) that were identified during the implementation>

Number	Category	Title	Description	Status	Risk Level	Risk Response Strategy	Actions / Measures	Target Date	Risk Owner
	Choose an item.		<i>Shortly</i>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			Choose an item.

2.2. Major Issues and Actions Taken

<This section should give an overview of the work package issues – existing obstacles>

Number	Category	Title	Description	Status	Size	Actions/ Measures	Target Date	Issue Owner
	Choose an item.		<i>Shortly</i>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			Choose an item.

2.3. Scope Changes (optional - only in case major changes are needed)

<This section should give an overview of the work package scope changes that need to be escalated to the Management, for the reporting period>

Number	Category	Title	Description	Status	Action Details (effort & responsible)	Priority	Actual Delivery Date
	Choose an item.			Choose an item.		Choose an item.	

2.4. Achievements (optional)

<This section should provide an overview of what has been achieved that haven't been yet referred in this document, focus exclusively on the reporting period>

Project Highlights / Achievements	Comments

3. Appendix 1: References and Related Documents

<Use this section to reference any relevant or additional information. Specify each reference or related>

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	<Example of a related document> <D1.1...>	<Example of a location> Link to shared folder
2		

All work package Progress Reports will be integrated as part of the Project Quality Reviews. Regular monitoring allows 1) assessment if the project is being carried out within scope, at the desired quality and according to the pre-defined schedule, 2) application of corrective actions if necessary.

5.3.2. PROJECT QUALITY REVIEWS

Quality reviews will be conducted by consolidating the collected information every 6 months (from 6-month WP progress report), analyzing it, completing a Quality checklist, and providing recommendations for improvement. Project quality reviews will be performed to verify that all project plans and processes are executed as planned and at the expected quality. Internal reporting is to monitor the project's technical progress. It is a summary of the technical work completed, progress on the work which is ongoing as well as an explanation for any deviations from the GA.

A Quality Review Checklist will be used to assess the project's compliance with the planned activities in different domains: scope, time, cost, quality, project organization, communications, risks, and end-user satisfaction. The findings based on the Quality Review will be presented during Project Meetings and to the General Assembly. PMO will, in addition, keep proper logs and registers for related risks, issues, decisions, and changes. The described procedure will allow the determination of the effectiveness of project processes, leading to potential improvements in processes, and analysis of the results – all concluded in Quality Review Report.

Reviews and all related quality assurance activities may result in change requests for corrective or preventive actions, updates in project documentation, improving the quality of project activities

5.4. QUALITY CONTROL RECORDS

Quality Control will be conducted based on the regular monitoring and consolidation of results from the quality assurance activities. SEID AS is responsible for quality monitoring and controlling. The quality records (evidence that QM activities have been performed) are archived in the project workspace under the folder WP8 - Monitoring & Control.

5.5. PERIODIC REPORTING TO EC AND FINAL CLOSURE

5.5.1. PERIODIC REPORTING TO EC

PROJECT REPORTING PERIODS (RP) AND RELATED RESPONSIBILITIES

RP1: M1-18, to be followed by interim payment, RP2: M19-30, to be followed by interim payment, RP3: M31-42, to be followed by final payment. Periodic reporting should be organized by the Coordinator with the support of TM, PMO, administrative team and assigned project manager from Europroject for administrative and financial matters (if needed). All WP Leaders are responsible to provide relevant progress information for their respective WP, they organize the communication with their WP participants. The payment schedule and rules are described in section 7.2 Payments within ColdSpark® Consortium Agreement. EC may suspend payments and ask for changes, improvements, and additional explanations on any technical, administrative, or financial aspect of the submitted reports. Three project reviews with the EC are scheduled at the start of the project:

1. At month 18 - Project review 1 (PR1)
2. At month 30 - Project review 2 (PR2)
3. At month 42 - Project review 3 (PR3)

CONTINUOUS AND INFORMAL REPORTING

In addition to the obligation of submitting periodic reports to the EC, partners must regularly complete the Portal Continuous Reporting tool and inform the PO (through the Coordinator) about: status, progress, any potential risks and delays, questions and issues and other project-related topics.

PERIODIC REPORT – 1) FINANCIAL AND 2) TECHNICAL PART.

Each project partner-beneficiary (excluding associated partners) is obligated to complete and submit a financial statement to the EC. The technical report is a collaborative document consolidated for all partners (who provide relevant information) and submitted by the Coordinator. Reporting rules are described in Article 21 – Reporting within the Grant Agreement.

5.5.2. CLOSURE AND FINAL ACCEPTANCE

The purpose is to manage the final acceptance of the project, including all deliverables and to perform the administrative closure of the project. The final acceptance is obtained from the Project Coordinator (PC). Before the formal closure, the PC should report on project performance to the End Review Meeting and develop the expected reports (the administrative and financial closure is often happening right after the official end date).

Official reports should summarize project performance throughout the project lifecycle and describe the main risks, issues, constraints, opportunities, and lessons learned identified along the project. It can also identify stakeholders' satisfaction, and provided best practices and solutions implemented - maintained in a project repository, accessible for future projects. The administrative closure includes updating, reviewing, organising and archiving all project documentation and records. It also comprises the final project acceptance and the communication of the project end to the relevant stakeholders.

6. RISK MANAGEMENT

The risk management procedure described here aims to facilitate the identification and documentation of risks impacting the achievement of the project's objectives.

6.1. IDENTIFYING RISKS

An initial risk list has been created, during the proposal preparation stage, which can be updated regularly (Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part A, List of Critical Risks). For each risk from the initial risk list, the consortium made a first analysis identifying associated WP and mitigation measures. Risks will continue to emerge during the project implementation and a proper risk management plan and processes are needed.

6.2. ASSESSING RISKS

It is important to assess the impact of the identified risks in terms of their influence on the project objectives (risk level) and the likelihood of occurrence in order to plan any risk response measures.

A matrix (visualization tool, Table 5) is presented and will be used by WP Leaders and other partners to register open project risks. It will measure risks based on a likelihood scale which assesses the probability of an event (from unlikely to probable) and the severity of one (from acceptable when a risk is hardly felt to generally unacceptable when a risk may threaten a project's fulfilment). Severity and impact result in the degree of risk impact or the overall risk level which is a bottom-line measurement used to prioritize possible issues and raise red flags where necessary.

WP Leaders also identify risks during internal reporting and meetings. Risks will be presented, reviewed, modified, and resolved on a regular basis.

		SCALE OF SEVERITY		
		ACCEPTABLE (1)	TOLERABLE (2)	GENERALLY UNACCEPTABLE (3)
SCALE OF LIKELIHOOD	NOT LIKELY (1)	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM
	POSSIBLE (2)	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
	PROBABLE (3)	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH

Table 5 Risk Assessment Matrix

If at any point a risk of medium to high likelihood, high severity and respectively high impact is identified, the Project Coordinator will be immediately informed. The best solutions to manage the risk mitigation plan will be discussed with project partners. Any high-impact risk remaining unresolved will be discussed during Project meetings.

6.3. RESPONSE

This step aims at identifying and planning the actions to control the risks. The selection of risk response strategy will be based on the results of the risk assessment (risk level), the type of risk, the effects on the overall project objectives etc. The strategy/ies selected for each risk are documented by the PMO and discussed with involved partners.

6.4. CONTROL

All risks will be recorded by PMO in a risk register (Annex 2) with details of the identified individual project risks, including:

- Risk Identification and Description Section – this section will include risk category, title, description, and status, identified by an identification date.
- Risk Assessment Section – risk level (probability), risk owner and escalation.
- Risk Response Section – risk response strategy, action details (effort and responsible), target date, traceability/comments.

Down-drop menus are available in the register for some of the described above sections. The PMO will collect the information from the internal status and progress reports, during partner meetings or from email correspondence. The Risk Owner will report periodically the status of the risk and any response activities to PMO who will be responsible for 1) documenting any risk updates,

including new risks or actions, updating the status of response activities, changing risk levels based on mitigation actions, changing the assignment of actions, etc.; 2) reporting to PC, and GA's. Revision of the status of risks and related actions, and identification of new risks that can impact project milestones, deliverables, or objectives will be done during Project and PTC meetings. The goal is to monitor and control the implementation of the risk response activities while continuously monitoring the project environment for new risks or changes.

7. ISSUE MANAGEMENT

Issue management will ensure that issues that have a potential impact on project scope, time, cost, quality, risk, or stakeholder satisfaction are assessed and acted upon. Relevant issues, follow-up and key decisions will be documented to bring visibility and accountability. The issue management process falls under the responsibilities of the PMO.

7.1. IDENTIFYING ISSUES

Any issues arising should be documented (e.g., disagreements on the interpretation of requirements, difficulties achieving the set goals (e.g., in terms of time, resources or quality), and external effects that influence the project negatively). Issues can be identified and raised by any Project partner throughout the project lifecycle. Any feedback received from project stakeholders should also be taken into consideration. Communication channels such as meetings, emails, reports, etc. will be utilized.

7.2. ASSESSMENT AND MEASURES

Any issue should be assessed regarding its urgency, impact, and its resolution. When an issue arises, an initial assessment (informal) will be performed by the person who raised the issue. This informal assessment will consider dimensions like relation to a specific area, possible consequences, level of urgency and size/scope. PMO will eventually assign a detailed analysis of the issue to a project partner and document the proposed solution and decisions made.

7.3. CONTROL

A project issue log will be used to record and capture all details of the identified individual project issues, including:

- Issue Identification and Description Section – this section will include category, title, description, and status, identified by an identification date.

- Issue Assessment and Action Description – action details, urgency, impact, size, target date, issue owner, escalation, traceability/comments.

The measures include monitoring and control of the issues identified during the project to easily communicate them to the several project decisional levels, for remediation action approval or status updates. Issues will be documented and monitored by the PMO and discussed in Project and PTC meetings. Additional meetings can be organized if necessary. Issue owners report regularly to PMO and TM and PMO reports to PC and GAs.

8. CONCLUSIONS

PM brings direction to projects for the successful achievement of the planned results and impacts. Leadership and smooth communications, clear and well-defined procedures and rules allow and enable team members to provide their best efforts and achieve great and ambitious results. The document is describing strict project management and monitoring techniques and contributes to following critical paths for excellent project execution.

ANNEX 1 GANTT WORK PACKAGES

Figure 11 ColdSpark® GANTT work packages

ANNEX 2 RISK REGISTER

This template is based on Open PM² Template for Risk Register. It is adjusted for ColdSpark project, and content / guidelines in some of the sections are changed

Risk Identification and Description							Risk Response			Risk Response			
ID	Category	Title	Description	Status	Identified By	Identification Date	Risk Level	Risk Owner	Escalation	Risk Response Strategy	Action Details (effort & responsible)	Target Date	Traceability/Comments
Guidelines	<Risks can be organised in different categories such as Project progress, technical, financial, human resources, legal, other>	<Short title for the risk>	<Description of the risk including its causes, the kinds of problems that could result (potential effects), and risk dependencies.> <Because of (CONDITION), it might be that (EVENT), which will lead to (IMPACT).>			<Date when the risk was identified <dd/mm/yy>>			<Should the issue be escalated to the General Assembly?> <Yes> or <No>>		<Description of the mitigation action(s), including the objective, scope, deliverables, the person responsible and the estimated effort needed. >	<Date on which the risk response is expected to be implemented.>	<Related artefacts: - ID for the related mitigation tasks in the Project Plan - ID for related changes, issues or decisions (log entries) .>
R01													
R02													

Figure 12 Risk Register Template

ANNEX 3 ISSUE LOG

This template is based on Open PMF Template for Issue Log. It is adjusted for ColdSpark project, and content / guidelines in some of the sections are changed

Issue Identification and Description						Issue Assessment and Action Description								
ID	Category	Title	Description	Status	Identified By	Identification Date	Action Details (effort & responsible)	Urgency	Impact	Size	Target Date	Issue Owner	Escalation	Traceability/Comments
Guidelines	<i>(Issues can be organised in different categories such as Project progress, technical, financial, human resources, cost)</i>	<i>(Short title for the issue)</i>	<i>(Description of the issue, including how it came about (known risk, unknown risk, ...) and its impact on the project.)</i>			<i>(Date when the issue was raised or was identified (dd/mm/yy))</i>	<i>(Proposed strategy to handle the issue. For the remediation plan, the following main steps should be executed: - Identification of the non-conformities, impact and recommended actions; - Analysis of the different scenarios and associated resources, timetable and costs; - Selection of the most cost-effective action and assignment of responsibilities.)</i>				<i>(Date on which the issue is expected to be resolved (dd/mm/yy))</i>		<i>(Should the issue be escalated to the General Assembly (Yes) or (No))</i>	<i>(Related artifacts: - ID for the related task - ID for the related tasks in the Project Plan - ID for related changes in the change log)</i>
11														
12														

Figure 13 Issue Log Template